

DESTINATION EARTH CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT

Worksheet 2

Co-design diagnosis and the Data-Information-Value Framework

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents Phase 2 of the co-design process, dedicated to the Co-design diagnosis. It introduces the Data-Information-Value (DIV) Framework, which offers a structured and systematic approach for identifying, prioritising, and directing co-design needs within DestinE service development. Building on the foundations established in Phase 1 “Approaching Users”, the diagnosis phase helps service providers examine how data is transformed into information, how this information is mobilised in users’ contexts, and where value is ultimately created, or lost, within the ecosystem.

The DIV Framework serves as both an analytical lens and a design-support instrument. It enables service providers to characterise technical, organisational, and relational conditions that shape the data journey, from upstream digital infrastructure to downstream user practices. Through this representation, the framework helps reveal gaps, misalignments, and dependencies that require co-design efforts, offering a shared basis for structuring a coherent sequence of workshops focused on usefulness, operability, and usability. Applied iteratively, the DIV Framework supports a progressive deepening of understanding as user engagement evolves

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1. Introduction to the Diagnosis Phase

1.1. Introduction to the diagnosis phase

The diagnosis phase plays a central role in assessing co-design needs and setting the foundation for effective collaboration. Its main purpose is to analyse both the technical system and the relationships between the actors involved, in order to identify missing components, interdependencies, and key challenges. The results of this phase provide the basis for a coherent co-design action plan. The organisation of subsequent co-design interactions should be guided by this diagnostic work, as it largely determines the overall success of the co-design journey.

Establishing a comprehensive understanding of the co-design landscape requires a structured approach that operates across three complementary levels:

- **The technical system and its missing elements**
- **The processes and competencies required to complete and operate the system**
- **The actors and the interactions that connect them**

The co-design Toolkit supports a detailed diagnosis across these three dimensions through the Data-Information-Value (DIV) Framework. The framework represents the complete data journey, from raw data to information and end uses, and identifies the actors and competencies involved in each transformation step. It provides a shared basis for locating where co-design efforts are most relevant and for structuring a coherent sequence of workshops that connect data, information, and value creation.

Tested in various co-design contexts, including a large metropolitan use case, the DIV Framework has proven effective for analysing complex, multi-stakeholder ecosystems. By systematically examining how data is transformed into information and value, it helps service providers identify challenges, map actor interactions, and align co-design activities with stakeholder needs and value creation objectives.

1.2. Position of the Data-Information-Value Framework within the co-design workflow

By leveraging insights from the User Monitoring Framework deployed in phase #1 “Approaching Users”, the Data-Information-Value Framework forms the core of co-design phase #2 “Diagnosis” phase in the co-design journey.

1.3. Objectives

This framework should be applied after a conclusive Phase #1 “Approaching Users”. At this stage, the service developer benefits from a global overview of the potential usage ecosystem which helped identify key challenges and opportunities related to the exploitation of data. Phase #1 provided insights relationships, rules, and actors within the ecosystem.

In Phase #2 “Diagnosis”, by integrating this understanding with the Data-Information-Value Framework (Figure 1), the service developer can diagnose and design services that are better aligned with the ecosystem's needs, ensuring that data is effectively transformed into actionable information and ultimately valuable services for users. This deeper alignment allows the service developer to ensure that the transformation from raw data to actionable information is contextually relevant, addressing the specific demands, competencies, and dynamics of the user communities. It enables the creation of tailored services that are more likely to be adopted and resilient, as these consider both the practical realities of the ecosystem and the strategic

entry points where the service can deliver the most value. This co-design approach strengthens the potential for operational impact by ensuring that the services developed are directly informed by ecosystem insights, leading to more effective data transformation and exploitation.

2. Presentation of the tool

The diagnosis of each service relies on its representation within the Data-Information-Value (DIV) Framework, which models the complete data journey from raw data to information, to end-uses and identifies the actors involved in each transformation process.

Through this lens, the development of DestinE services can be understood as the progressive construction of relationships between data, information, and usage.

The DIV Framework provides a structured approach for analysing where co-design is most needed and how it should be directed. It helps service providers and project teams describe the technical and organisational ecosystem in which data circulates, is transformed, and acquires value. This diagnosis allows teams to identify missing components, gaps in competencies, or misalignments between the service concept and user contexts.

The tool serves both as a diagnostic map and as a design compass. As a diagnostic map, it offers a common representation of the service ecosystem that can be shared between service providers, DestinE, and end-users. As a design compass, it supports the structuring of subsequent co-design workshops from usefulness to operability and usability, ensuring that each step is informed by a coherent understanding of how data becomes value for users.

By applying the DIV Framework, service providers can:

- Analyse how data, information, and usage are currently linked in the targeted ecosystem.
- Identify the critical gaps and leverage points where co-design efforts are required.
- Translate technical and relational insights into a consistent co-design action plan.
- Establish a shared foundation for dialogue between data providers, developers, and users.

This framework is therefore both an analytical tool and a coordination mechanism. It creates continuity between the technical, organisational, and relational dimensions of co-design, allowing the diagnosis phase to inform the entire co-design journey that follows.

2.1. Overview of the Data-Information-Value Framework

The DIV Framework distinguishes six complementary components, each describing a key layer in the transformation from data to value. Analysing these components in sequence allows teams to locate gaps, dependencies, and opportunities for improvement, ensuring that co-design efforts are targeted and coherent.

In contrast with conventional approaches that start from available data and move downstream toward potential uses, the co-design approach begins upstream, with users and their needs. It first identifies who the users are, what value they seek to create or reinforce, and how DestinE can contribute to that value through its infrastructure and services. Only then does it explore which data and processing capabilities are required to enable that value. This inversion of perspective is essential: it ensures that data exploitation is driven by relevance and purpose, rather than by availability alone, and that every technical decision is grounded in a clear understanding of user contexts and expected outcomes.

Figure 1. Representation of the “Data-Information-Value Framework”

1. Usage ecosystem (User needs, ecosystem dynamics...)

This component anchors the entire framework in the needs and constraints of the intended user communities. It identifies the problems, expectations, and success criteria that guide the design and evaluation of services. In the context of DestinE, this involves understanding how specific stakeholders such as environmental agencies, local authorities, or policy bodies define the relevance and usefulness of the services developed on the platform.

2. Value-embedding usage

This component focuses on how the service produces concrete value for users once information becomes part of their practices. It assesses the benefits created in terms of effectiveness, resilience, efficiency, or strategic capability. It also considers how users access, interpret, and mobilise this information in their operational workflows.

In the DestinE ecosystem, this includes the tools, interfaces, and mechanisms through which users interact with digital services (e.g. visualisation environments, APIs, or integrated applications) and the ways these elements support decision-making or daily operations. Analysing this component clarifies how data-driven insights lead to measurable outcomes for users, how they are embedded into existing practices, and what conditions must be met to ensure their adoption and sustained value creation.

3. Valuable information

This component refers to the processes that convert raw data into interpretable and relevant outputs. It includes analytical workflows, models, and transformations that generate meaningful information for users. Within DestinE, this may involve processing chains that derive climate indicators, predictive analytics, or scenario outputs from Digital Twin simulations. Analysing this stage helps identify how information is created, validated, and disseminated through the available technical environment.

4. Data

This component focuses on the raw datasets that constitute the foundation of the service. It examines data origin, quality, accessibility, and temporal or spatial resolution. Within DestinE, this includes Earth Observation data, model outputs, and other thematic datasets accessible through the platform. The objective is to understand which data streams can be mobilised, what gaps exist, and how these datasets can be harmonised to serve the intended application.

5. Digital infrastructure

This component describes the technical environment that enables the collection, processing, and delivery of data and information. It encompasses the DestinE Platform, the Data Lake, computational resources, and interoperability mechanisms. Analysing this layer helps clarify

what digital assets and tools are available, how they interconnect, and what dependencies or technical interfaces must be considered for service development.

Why distinguishing components matters

Each component plays a critical role in value creation. By differentiating between Digital Infrastructure, Data, Valuable Information, Value-Embedding usage, and Users' needs, the diagnostic can ensure that every stage of co-design addresses specific aspects of the ecosystem, transforming raw data into services that truly meet user needs. This differentiation is especially helpful in identifying gaps or improvement areas, making the co-design process more structured and responsive to real-world challenges.

2.2. Applying the framework in practice: Step-by-step diagnosis guide

To apply this framework effectively, use it progressively and build directly on the outputs of Phase 1. All materials from the Approaching Users phase including the User Monitoring Framework, stakeholder and competencies mapping, project ID cards and preliminary ecosystem insights should feed into this diagnosis. It is designed to be filled out in phases, beginning with the initial diagnostic stage and evolving as the relationship with users deepens, and feedback is integrated. Below is a step-by-step guide, aligning with the main components of the framework, to support a structured and comprehensive diagnostic approach:

1. Usage ecosystem

- **Objective:** Understand the broader environment in which the service will be deployed, including key stakeholders, data flows, regulations, and ecosystem dynamics. Determine the technical skills and limitations of users to ensure information is accessible and actionable.
- **How to fill:** Start by mapping out relevant actors (e.g., local authorities, health organizations, environmental agencies), the relationships between them, and their roles in data use and service deployment. This helps identify primary data sources, regulatory constraints, and opportunities for collaboration. Assess users' current technical skills, knowledge gaps, and training needs. This understanding enables the design of interfaces, visualizations, and tools that meet users at their current skill level, enhancing usability and service adoption.
- **Example:** For an air quality monitoring service, identify key stakeholders (city councils, public health bodies, and environmental agencies), relevant data sources (satellite and sensor data), and regulations that govern data use. This mapping reveals the primary interactions, constraints, and potential pathways for service impact. Health officials may need a simplified dashboard with visual summaries rather than raw data feeds, making the information more accessible and actionable for their specific needs.

2. Value-embedding usage and valuable information

- **Objective:** Define service offerings that address the needs and challenges identified in the ecosystem analysis. Monitor the evolving relationship between the service team and users to ensure alignment, trust, and collaborative engagement.

- **How to fill:** Based on the ecosystem mapping and user competencies, outline potential services that could meet user needs and their first components (e.g., dashboards, alerts, or analysis tools). Include clear descriptions of how each service creates value and fits into users' workflows. Track all interactions, feedback between service providers, platform, and users. Document progress in relationship-building, identify challenges in communication, and adjust approaches as needed. A strong relationship enables iterative feedback that refines and improves service design.
- **Example:** Develop a real-time air quality monitoring dashboard using a custom-designed model that combines CAMS regional and global data, land use and local monitoring data into high-resolution air quality forecasts for city councils that includes visualizations, predictive alerts, and summaries that are easy to interpret and integrate into decision-making processes. Conduct regular feedback sessions with health department representatives, using their input to iteratively improve the dashboard and ensure it meets operational needs.

3. Data and digital infrastructure - Service developer ability to provide the required service (prototype/operational)

- **Objective:** Assess the technical, infrastructural, and organizational capacities that enable the service to be developed, deployed, and maintained. Ensure that the proposed service is not only conceptually relevant but also technically and operationally feasible within the DestinE ecosystem. Identify where additional co-design or partnership efforts are needed to reinforce critical capabilities. Evaluate the service developer technical and resource capabilities to ensure effective service delivery.
- **How to fill:** Evaluate which datasets are available within DestinE (e.g., through the Data Lake, Digital Twins, or federated sources), their quality, resolution, update frequency, and licensing conditions. Identify whether these data streams are sufficient to produce the expected information and which additional datasets or external sources would be required. Examine the computing and storage resources available to the service developer. Assess the compatibility of existing processing chains, models, and APIs with the platform environment. Clarify what technical elements such as workflows, algorithms, or visualization tools must be developed or adapted to support the prototype or operational service. Analyse the service team's composition, competencies, and available resources. Identify the key technical, analytical, and facilitation skills required, as well as potential dependencies on external partners. Assess whether the current configuration allows for the transition from a prototype to an operational service, and whether long-term maintenance and data governance can be ensured.
- **Example:** Identify that continuous service delivery requires high-frequency, quality-controlled data streams and scalable computing capacity. Establish a formal linkage between the service developer's processing environment and the DestinE Data Lake to access near-real-time datasets, ensuring synchronization with Digital Twin outputs. Where gaps persist, formalize partnerships with external data or infrastructure providers to guarantee the operational continuity, interoperability, and sustainability of the service..

2.3. Structuring a consistent co-design journey based on the co-design diagnosis

The primary objective of the co-design diagnosis is to identify the issues that must be addressed throughout the co-design process. Its purpose is not to document what is already known, stabilized, or functioning, but rather to make visible the *unknowns*: the elements that remain unclear, insufficiently defined, uncertain, or that require further exploration before any meaningful design work can take place. By systematically revealing these zones of ambiguity, the diagnosis establishes the foundation upon which a coherent and purposeful co-design journey can be built.

Once these problematic or still poorly defined elements have been surfaced through the DIV Framework, the service provider can organize a structured sequence of co-design actions. The issues revealed by the DIV typically fall within the five major types of challenges commonly encountered during service development (see Figure 1). Each of these challenges corresponds to a distinct layer or discontinuity along the Data–Information–Value journey, and each requires the involvement of specific stakeholders and design efforts to be progressively resolved.

As a result, the identification of these challenges directly informs the architecture of the co-design journey. Typically, solving issues respectively related to service usefulness and to service operability may require to gather different types of stakeholders in different workshops with different purposes.

Figure 2. The five key technical challenges to be addressed through co-design workshops

Identifying co-design issues through the DIV Framework is a pivotal step for transitioning from the diagnostic phase to the construction of a relevant co-design journey. While it may be tempting to assume that every co-design process can follow a single, generic, and replicable pathway, the reality is that the challenges to be addressed vary significantly across projects. Each service development context presents its own discontinuities, uncertainties, and constraints along the Data–Information–Value chain.

The core logic of the co-design diagnosis is therefore to identify the specific configuration of issues that characterizes each project.

In the following, some typical examples are given to illustrate how co-design diagnosis and the DIV framework can help to identify specific co-design issues and to structure the co-design journey accordingly (for more detail about the specific features of each type of co-design workshop, please see the worksheet 3):

- 1) **Defining the scope of usefulness** relies on identifying consistent potential users and the specific problems DestinE could help them to solve. On the DIV framework, issues related to usefulness typically position on the left side, being either related to usage ecosystem, value embedding usage or the relationship between these two components. The diagnosis can unveil a variety of issues related to this challenge that leads to different co-design settings, including for instance:
 - **Ex 1** - *The users could have a clear idea on which needs could be addressed. In such case, workshops should be organized with users to establish clear requirements to address those needs.*
 - **Ex 2** - *Contrarily, the users could have no clear idea on which needs could be addressed. In such case, workshops should be organized with users to help users to understand the potential value of DestinE and to formulate specific needs that could be addressed.*
- 2) **Ensuring operability on the DestinE Platform** relates to making sure that the service to be designed suits the platform resources, data and protocols, so that it can run on it and/or be designed based on it. On the DIV framework, issues related to operability typically position on the right side, being either related digital infrastructure, data and/or valuable information. The diagnosis can unveil a variety of issues related to this challenge that leads to different co-design settings, including for instance:
 - **Ex 1** – *Existing generic services and/or dataset that would help to address the targeted needs can already be integrated on the platform. In such case, workshops could be organized with the manager of these assets to understand how to access and adapt these services and/or datasets to serve the specific targeted needs.*
 - **Ex 2** – *Contrarily, addressing user needs can require leveraging services and/or datasets that are not already available on the platform. In such case, workshops could be organized with the manager of the platform to explore how to integrate these on the platform.*
- 3) **Fostering service usability** relies on clarifying the processes and tools impacted by the service, so as to ensure that the service will be usable and adopted by users. On the DIV framework, issues related to usability typically position on the middle, being either related to data, valuable information, value embedding usage or the relationship between these components. The diagnosis can unveil a variety of issues related to this challenge that leads to different co-design settings, including for instance:
 - **Ex 1** – *Users may be familiar with digital applications in their daily work and even have some competencies in Geographical Information Systems (GIS), such as QGIS or others. In such case, workshops could be organized with users to understand how the service to be designed can be interfaced with these existing tools, building on user competencies.*
 - **Ex 2** – *Contrarily, the users may be completely foreign to the use of digital tools and data in their daily work. In such a case, workshops could be organized with*

users to understand how the user experience could be adapted to ease the adoption of the service.

- 4) **Supporting service scalability** relies on providing options for use in other contexts, with other stakeholders and even for other purposes. Note that scalability might require specific actions related to usefulness, usability and operability all along the course of co-design. Therefore, on the DIV framework, issues related to scalability can unfold on every component, and usually imply specific workshops related these components. The diagnosis can unveil a variety of issues related to this challenge that leads to different co-design settings, including for instance:
- **Ex 1** – *The requirements may correspond to very generic needs encountered by a variety of users. In such case, workshops could be organized with the targeted users and/or other potential users to understand their profile and tailor engagement mechanisms towards scalability.*
 - **Ex 2** – *Contrarily, the needs to be addressed can be very specific to the targeted users. However, in such a case, some technical bricks might be generalized as to serve other specific needs of other users. Therefore, workshops could be organized with other potential users to identify these bricks and design the architecture of the service in a way that fosters the subsequent reuse of these bricks.*
- 5) **Ensuring service sustainability** relies on designing solutions that remain viable, maintainable, and accessible over time. This includes anticipating long-term technical needs, setting up appropriate governance and maintenance mechanisms, and involving users not only as testers but as long-term partners, potentially through contractual relationships. Sustainability can also require addressing intellectual property arrangements, cost structures, and the capacity to update or evolve the service as user needs, regulations, or technological environments change. Therefore, service sustainability requires an alignment of every component of the DIV framework. The diagnosis can unveil a variety of issues related to this challenge that lead to different co-design settings, including for instance:
- **Ex 1** – *The service may require long-term operational support involving multiple partners (e.g., platform managers, data providers, or external contractors). In such a case, workshops could include the clarification of maintenance responsibilities, establishing update cycles, and negotiating formal arrangements (e.g., SLAs, licensing conditions, support agreements) to secure the long-term robustness of the service.*
 - **Ex 2** – *In other cases, sustainability may depend on the users' ability to internalise part of the service maintenance or contribute to its evolution. Workshops could then be organised with users to identify the competencies, resources, or organisational arrangements they need to sustain the service over time, and to co-design training, documentation, or governance mechanisms that support autonomy and continuity.*

2.4. Timing and progressive use of the framework

The Data-Information-Value (DIV) Framework is not designed to be completed in a single step. It is a dynamic and evolving tool that grows alongside the co-design process. It should be progressively refined as relationships with users deepen, as new insights emerge, and as service prototypes evolve.

During the **initial diagnostic phase**, the framework helps gather foundational information about the usage ecosystem, user competencies, and the initial types of services that could be developed. At this stage, the focus is on uncovering unknowns, identifying potential entry points for collaboration, and defining the baseline requirements for service design. This involves conducting meetings with users and stakeholders, exploring their operational environments, and collecting early data on their needs and challenges. The expected outcome is a preliminary mapping of the ecosystem and a first outline of possible service directions.

In the **continuous monitoring and update phase**, the framework serves as a living document that captures how relationships, requirements, and design hypotheses evolve over time. Regular engagement with users enables the framework to be updated as new information becomes available through workshops, interviews, and iterative testing. This ensures that the Service Developer–User relationship remains active and that the developer’s ability to deliver the service is continuously aligned with emerging insights. The result is an evolving representation that documents changes in user needs, technical constraints, and the adaptability of the service, supporting continuous improvement.

Finally, the **final documentation and assessment phase** consolidates the complete co-design journey. Once the service approaches deployment, the framework is used to document the entire data journey from acquisition to actionable information and operational value. It records the rationale behind each decision, the dependencies identified along the way, and the lessons learned throughout the process. This final version provides a transparent trace of the design logic and serves as a foundation for future refinement, scalability, or replication of the service in new contexts.

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